

THE DESCRIPTION OF CHRONOTOPE IN LITERATURE

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Abstract. This article presents the chronotope, which is the basis of fiction, that is, the depiction of space and time in a work. It claims that every work is situated in a specific location or period of time and feeds the reader's mind. The viewpoints of world scholars on this topic are expressed. It is stressed that the way that creative time is portrayed in literature depends on a number of factors, including the genre and nature of the literary work, the author's viewpoint, their style, and the reader's metaphorical interpretation of the time period that the work portrays.

Key words: fiction, art, space, time, literary work, plot, artist, theory.

Introduction. The science of literary criticism is aware that time and space are essential components of the reality that will emerge in a piece of art. If we look at it from a vital perspective, a farmer plants the seeds of blessing and toils diligently till a plentiful crop is produced. Space and time are like water and air for this process to happen, to start and finish. If we compare a creator to a farmer, the fundamental reality that has been incorporated into his work produces such fruit that it feeds people's spiritually, heart, and soul rather than their stomach. "It is natural that the events that form the links in the chain of the plot of a literary work occur in a specific place and time."¹ This law of fiction is distinct. Plots in fiction that follow this law are detailed. It is well recognized that the philosophical ideas of space and time play a crucial role in the emergence of global events. "Space and time are the general forms of existence of being; time expresses the sequential occurrence and duration of events and processes occurring in the world, while space expresses the order, scope, and scale of the objects that comprise the world as well as the relative location of their structural points"².

At a given time, there is micro-reality of a single moment in addition to continuous events that happen consecutively. For instance, the creative can be inspired and excited by a lightning strike, a leaf shattering, a splash of water, etc. This demonstrates how fiction uses life as a resource in addition to describing it. Writers, or word artists, are so skilled at capturing this small reality on paper that they produce amazing works of art. Reflecting objective real time, the idea of time is a conceptually complicated complete system. Numerous theoretical and conceptual perspectives, methods, and interpretations of the phenomena of time exist in the fields of philosophy, physics, religion, literary and aesthetic sciences, and art because of its complexity. Philosophy starts with the idea that time is an essential component of the world and a property of the universe. This is because time is an objectively actual form of the universe-matter rather than the primary form of any existence, like space or, more

¹Boboyev T. Adabiyotshunoslik asoslari.-T.: O'zbekiston. 2002. 133-bet.

²Falsafa. Ensiklopediklug'at. -T.: Sharq. 2010. P-271.

accurately, the basic form of phenomena. As a form of life of matter, it characterizes the continuity of the existence of all objects, the continuity of processes in the material world (the set of objective processes that have occurred, are occurring, and will occur in the future, which underlies the continuous existence and development of the world), the consistency of the exchange of states, the continuous interconnection, dimensionality, and order of events that have occurred over time, or, more simply, the order of the sequence of events.

The creative discovery of artistic reality itself, the artistic time, which is its practical form of existence, becomes the art of art, or the aesthetics of art. This is the conclusion of the conceptual brief note on the theory of time. This is because any category of philosophy, the dialectic of laws, is always the theoretical and methodological basis, the source for all systems and types of science. Therefore, universal categories like space and time are legitimately considered, including literary and aesthetic categories. After all, the basis for the classification of art into categories was that very time and space. G.E. Lessing initially highlighted this philosophical and artistic issue in his essay "Laocoon, or On the Boundaries of Painting and Poetry." M.M. Bakhtin came up with the scientific postulate that "everything in this world is time, space, a real chronotope" based on this fact³.

Regardless of the literary genre or type to which it belongs, literature has been artistically perfected since its inception as a model of art through the creative and aesthetic mastery of time and space as a separate aspect of artistic reality, a particular phenomenon of the work's artistic texture, and one of the active means of organizing its content. The master of the artistic word exemplifies the art of artistically free use of artistic time and artistic space based on his creative intention. For example, he may squeeze centuries into a day and a day into a century, find time and space in a new literary way, and freely use them as he pleases. Like the actual reality it mirrors, the artistic world is temporally and spatially situated. In order to ensure the holistic perception of the literary and poetic reality created by the author in the work—creative and aesthetic assimilation, or the perception of artistic reality in its complete integrity—and to form the composition of the work, the time of this world becomes the most significant characteristic of the artistic image.

The dynamic arts are the group that includes fiction. As a textual consistency of the work, the literary-poetic picture is formally produced in both time and space. Its substance, however, represents the time-space "model" of the universe as a symbolic totality. For this reason, a piece of art is referred to as a record of the rhythm of images in space and time. The researcher highlights that "the image is given in such a sense, of course, that any of its content is associated with someone, somewhere, and at some time⁴". The three dimensions of the creative universe are these three basic quantities that the writer needs. The picture cannot appear without these unchangeable numbers.

Artistic time in literature is represented as a system that is captured in the speech, movement, and artistic and aesthetic mastery of a given period of time. This means the

³Del Rey, Lester (1980). "The World of Science Fiction". – P.: Garland Publishing. 1926—1976. – P. 91-93.

⁴James A.W. Heffernan. Space and time in literature and the visual arts. *Soundings: An Interdisciplinary Journal*, Vol. 70, No. 1/2, 1987. pp. 95–119.

existence of the literary hero, who is the subject of the image as we have mentioned above is called perceived time. In terms of literary perception, the hero of the literature exists in the dimension of time which is termed as conceived time is the modeled reality integrated in suitable forms for the audience to be able to appreciate. In literature, the author's worldview, the author's style, the type and genre of the literary text, and even the reader's figurative interpretation of the time within the work all reflect a form of artistic time. Life can neither be represented over a prolonged span of time, nor over an extended period. This way of visualizing life creates a sense of perpetual uneasiness. Hence, it is essential to represent time in an artwork as fleeting. In a given piece of work, "the reader's image gets decorated with depth," an aesthetic order is arranged, and the work is "spreading". The author had the command of deliberately slow down (retardation technique), compress, condense (actualization of the moment), or completely stop (in portraits, landscape images, in the philosophical commentary of the author) the flow of time. Indeed, time organization disposition is achieved through division and continuity and thus, time is always artistic as well as real. The change is not in one direction but is marked and directed by the peculiarity of the author's idea which synthesizes the artistic image as well as the subjective and objective along with the domains, organizes the work, speech and lapse for completion in total. Not just that, the artistic period, like its sculptural modeling, depends on the nature of the genre, the literary style, imagination of the author and the literary movements and styles created during that period. Thus, the system of artistic periods – forms, types, categories, and even approaches stemming from the author's creative and philosophical purpose is marked by richness and variety. Due to the fact that the "model" of the flow of time in a piece of art is created from the author's perspective which is the controlling element of the spatio-temporal relations in the text, it follows that the author's artistic world is at the center of his artistic expression of the "model." On this ground, "all alterations in the artistic period are encapsulated in a single line of its enhancement with regards to the general progress of oratory art"⁵

The dialectic of time and space provides the basis for the status of the fourth dimension of a work of art. The existence of space and time being correlated to each other and not independent are two separate entities, as Einstein's theory of relativity proclaims. To him, "The current moment in time is represented as a single point on a Euclidean multifaceted plane space which the universe is made of. Alongside, time also has its own singular moment in a specific place which together form an archetype dimension. So, in such complex forms of existence as space and time, material changes have to occur for it to function." Firstly, there are no material systems or processes that lack continuity, nor do they remain unchanged from the past to the future. Secondly, the interconnectedness of time and space becomes apparent through movement. In literature, artistic time, much like artistic space, is a fundamental aspect of the world the artist portrays. Artistic space is lively and dynamic, as it fosters an environment for movement, while artistic time corresponds with space (thus, in movement, time and space are interconnected, resulting in a unique time-space continuum for the

⁵To'ychiyev A. Hikoyalardamakonzavamontasviri // Til va adabiyot ta'limi. 2009-yil. 11-son. 32-bet.

characters). This is why dynamics is considered essential to the relationship between space and time. All static spaces must be incorporated into the timeline of the events being portrayed.

Conclusion. The issues of space and time hold significant relevance in art and literature, showcasing the extensive range of possibilities within these fields (as well as in aesthetics and literary analysis). Typically, any artistic work presents a developed representation of space and time to some degree. After all, the purpose of art is to represent the world in its entirety, that is, in the fusion of spatial and temporal coordinates. The combination of spatial and temporal elements plays a role in the intellectual and tangible structure of the artistic chronotope. In this context, time becomes malleable and artistically evident. Additionally, space accelerates. Time, events, and narratives are extended in their motion. The characteristics of time are revealed through space, while space is experienced and understood in relation to time..

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